

TEACHERS' PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES IN A CATHOLIC UNIVERSITY

Mark N. Langcay, Ed.D.

Junior High School, University of Saint Louis Tuguegarao, Cagayan, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10800346>

ABSTRACT

In the educational landscape, pedagogy is considered as one of the pillars of education for it shapes the teaching and learning process, ensuring that learners acquire the knowledge, skills, and values necessary for their personal and professional development. The study aimed to assess the pedagogical practices of teachers during the pre-pandemic up to the present. This study utilized a quantitative type of research, specifically descriptive survey method to describe the pedagogical practices of teachers. Findings revealed that teachers often practiced the following pedagogies: collaborative, reflective, and inquiry-based methods. Teachers' pedagogical practices have a significant difference along the personal profile such as sex, department, field/ specialization, and number of years in teaching. Lastly, teachers' pedagogical practices have a significant difference along academic profile such as number of trainings attended related to instructional pedagogy, type of school from which bachelor's degree was obtained, subject taught, and type of education. With that, continuing professional development is deemed to be significant to upskill teachers in advancing them in both conventional and unconventional settings as 21st century education would demand.

Keywords: *Pedagogical Practices; Catholic University; Flexible Learning*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers play a pivotal role in the educational process. Hence, teachers establish the tone and light in the teaching and learning process by employing a variety of pedagogies to promote active learning among learners. Thus, to achieve the intended

targets and outcomes, implementers of pedagogies must carefully plan their instructions. In connection, pedagogy is crucial because it provides teachers with knowledge of the ideal procedures for a classroom environment. It enables them to comprehend how various learners learn to modify their lesson to meet these demands. Since the learners would find pedagogies engaging, this will enhance their teaching effectiveness in activating learners' knowledge and skills (Ali, Mondal & Das, 2018; Archambault, Leary, & Rice, 2022).

However, with the spread of COVID-19 which resulted to the closure of educational institutions worldwide (United Nations, 2020; UNESCO 2021). This closure has spurred the development of online learning environments within these schools, ensuring that learning is not disrupted. The coronavirus pandemic put the centers' abilities to deal with a crisis that required educational modification to cope with the challenges (Reimers, 2022; Courtney, Miller, & Gisondo, 2022). Moreover, to maintain the continuity of learning and to intensely promote learners' acquisition for the optimum of their abilities in the new normal of education, 21st century education is necessary. Thus, for both instructors and learners to succeed, they must be equipped with adequate information, skills, and competencies (Butola, 2021; De los Reyes, Blannin, Cohrsen, & Mahat, 2022). Hence, this can only be achieved if teachers are able to give quality instruction while employing suitable pedagogies to accelerate learning in the face of ambiguity (O'Keefe, Rafferty, Gunder, & Vignare, 2020).

Pedagogy comes from the Italian word "pedagogia" which means the art and knowledge of teaching learners (Putri & Elihami, 2021). Hence, pedagogy is the center of the educational reform movement. It has been the beginning point for integrating modern concepts about learning and teaching, as well as the relevance of ideas to twenty-first-century educators (Compayré & Payne, 2015; Pham & Philip, 2021; Ginsburg & Megahed, 2021). A teaching strategy known as pedagogy involves teachers instructing learners both in theory and in practice. Pedagogy is influenced by educators' teaching philosophies and includes their knowledge of cultural differences and various learning styles. To consolidate earlier knowledge, it is crucial for students to create meaningful classroom relationships (Brown, Boda, Lemmi, & Monroe, 2019; Rippé, Weisfeld-Spolter, Yurova, & Kemp, 2021).

In the 21st century educational parlance, pedagogy plays a very critical role in the success of teaching and learning. However, literatures suggest that one of the main reasons why there is a decline of the quality of education being provided to the students is the misuse and abuse of pedagogical techniques, especially on the utilization of different instructional strategies of teachers (Sato & Loewen, 2019; Usanov & Qayumov, 2020). Furthermore, there is also a need to revisit teachers' use of pedagogies in their classes especially during the implementation of distance learning and flexible learning which is brought by the COVID-19 pandemic. There are issues that were found in literature that teachers did not provide responsive online learning strategies and techniques to their students because of some external and internal factors and issues (Yates, et al., 2021; Serdyukov, 2015; Terenko & Ogienko, 2020). Moreover, teachers' teaching quality has deteriorated because of inappropriate use of instructional

techniques, methods, and procedures. Learners became passive recipients and partakers of knowledge, which resulted to low academic performance (Ezra, Cohen, Bronshtein, Gabbay, & Baruth, 2021; LaTour & Noel, 2021).

This university, a higher education institution in Northern Luzon, already embraced the use of flexible learning since 2016 with the use of its Learning Management System. However, the full implementation took place last March 2020 due to the effect of the COVID-19. During its full implementation, students and teachers were exposed to flexible learning with the use of online learning as its main learning modality. With the gradual implementation of the full face-to-face learning, the university shifted to Expanded-Inclusive Flexible Learning (E-IFLEX). With the implementation of these learning modalities, it is important to assess the utilization of pedagogies, with emphasis on instructional strategies to ensure responsiveness of these to the needs of students. Hence, this study was conducted to assess pedagogical practices of teachers during the pre-pandemic up to the present.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the pedagogical practices of teachers during the pre-pandemic up to the present. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the personal and academic profile of teachers?
2. What are the pedagogical practices of teachers during the pre-pandemic up to the present along the following:
 - 2.1 Constructivist
 - 2.2 Collaborative
 - 2.3 Integrative
 - 2.4 Reflective
 - 2.5 Inquiry-Based Learning
3. Is there a significant difference on the pedagogical practices of the respondents when grouped according to their profile variables?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a quantitative type of research specifically the descriptive survey method to describe the pedagogical practices of teachers. This study was conducted in a private higher education institution in Northern Philippines. The respondents were 227 teachers across all departments.

A checklist was used to gather the personal and academic profile of the respondents. A validated questionnaire was used to determine the pedagogical practices of teachers. The said questionnaire consists of 30 items and divided into five major dimensions which include the following: Constructivist method (6 items), Collaborative method (6 items); Integrative method (6 items); Reflective method (6 items); and Inquiry-based learning

method (6 items). The said tool had undergone content validation by research experts and reliability test prior to its administration.

The data were analyzed using frequency counts and percentage to describe the profile of the respondents, weighted mean to identify the pedagogical practices of teachers, independent sample t-test and one way analysis of variance to determine the significant difference on the pedagogical practices of teachers when grouped according to their profile variables.

RESULTS

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percent
A. Personal Profile		
Sex		
Male	94	41.40
Female	133	58.60
Age		
< 25 years old	44	19.40
25 - 29	107	47.10
30 - 34	26	11.50
35 - 39	11	4.90
40 - 44	20	8.80
45 - 49	13	5.70
≥ 50	6	2.60
Mean Age = 30 years old		
Civil Status		
Single	157	69.20
Married	69	30.40
Widowed	1	0.40
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	129	56.80
Master's Degree	88	38.80
Doctoral Degree	10	4.40
Department		
Elementary	24	10.60
JHS (Junior High School)	59	26.00
SHS (Senior High School)	30	13.20
SABH (School of Accountancy, Business, and Hospitality)	18	7.90
SEAITE (School of Engineering, Architecture, and Information Technology Education)	37	16.30
SEAS (School of Education, Arts, and Sciences)	34	15.00

SHAS (School of Health and Allied Sciences)	20	8.80
SGS-CPD (School of Graduate Studies and Continuing Professional Development)	5	2.20
Field/Specialization		
Teacher Education	125	55.10
Social Science and Humanities	16	7.00
Health and Allied Sciences	23	10.10
Business and Hospitality Management	20	8.80
Engineering and Architecture	31	13.70
Information Technology and Related Discipline	12	5.30
No. of Years in Teaching		
< 1 year	13	5.80
1 - 3	95	42.00
4 - 6	54	23.90
7 - 9	15	6.60
≥ 10 years	49	21.70
Ave. No. of Years in Teaching = 6 years		
B. Academic Profile		
No. of training attended related to instructional pedagogy for the past five years		
0 - 5	86	37.90
6 - 10	56	24.70
11 - 15	38	16.70
16 - 20	22	9.70
≥ 21	25	11.00
Type of school from which the teacher obtained his/her bachelor's degree		
SUC/LUC	59	26.00
Catholic HEIs	146	64.30
Private HEIs	22	9.70
Subject/s previously taught		
Language and Literature	36	15.90
Music, Arts, PE, and Health	14	6.20
Economics and Livelihood Education	8	3.50
Mathematics	20	8.80
Allied Health Sciences	31	13.70
Christian Formation Education	23	10.20
Business and Accounting	17	7.50
Professional Education	2	0.90
Social Sciences Discipline and General Education	25	11.10
Research Discipline	6	2.70
Information Communications Technology	13	5.80
Law	4	1.80
Psychology	3	1.30

Engineering and Applied Sciences	17	7.50
Hospitality Management	3	1.30
Architecture	4	1.80
Type of Education		
Teacher Education Graduate	129	56.80
Non-Education Graduate with LET	10	4.40
Non-Education Graduate without LET	88	38.80

Table 2
Summary of Pedagogical Practices of Teachers

Pedagogical Practices	Mean	Description
Constructivist Method	4.50	Always Practiced
Collaborative Method	4.43	Often Practiced
Integrative Method	4.51	Always Practiced
Reflective Method	4.01	Often Practiced
Inquiry-Based Method	4.45	Often Practiced

Table 3.a
Test of Significant Difference on Teachers' Pedagogical Practices When Grouped by Personal Profile

Personal Profile	Group	Constructivist			Collaborative			Integrative			Reflective			Inquiry-Based		
		Mean	t/F value	p-value	Mean	t/F value	p-value	Mean	t/F value	p-value	Mean	t/F value	p-value	Mean	t/F value	p-value
Sex	Male	4.41	2.49	.013	4.35	2.00	.044	4.40	2.08	.039	3.95	1.02	.318	4.43	.603	.547
	Female	4.46			4.48			4.56			4.05			4.47		
Age	< 25	4.52			4.43			4.53			4.08			4.47		
	25 - 29	4.52	.581	.746	4.46	.388	.886	4.53	.275	.948	4.05	.613	.719	4.51	1.511	.176
	30 - 34	4.42			4.39			4.49			3.83			4.42		

	35 - 39	4.48			4.38			4.41			3.86			4.26		
	40 - 44	4.56			4.34			4.55			4.05			4.41		
	45 - 49	4.49			4.49			4.47			3.96			4.46		
	≥ 50	4.25			4.28			4.39			3.72			4.00		
Civil Status	Single	4.49	.95	.34	4.42	.39	.69	4.48	1.69	.09	4.03	.39	.69	4.46	.01	.99
	Married	4.55	.51	.43	4.45	.44	.94	4.59	.63	.92	4.09	.95	.93	4.46	.10	.92
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	4.51			4.44			4.53			3.96			4.49		
	Master's Degree	4.51	2.15	.18	4.40	.18	.83	4.51	1.02	.36	4.08	.72	.48	4.11	1.27	.28
	Doctoral Degree	4.22			4.42			4.33			4.02			4.30		
Department	Elementary	4.73			4.59			4.63			4.22			4.46		
	JHS	4.75	8.97	.00	4.62	5.45	.00	4.74	6.30	.00	4.27	5.51	.00	4.70	5.60	.00
	SHS	4.58			4.52			4.59			4.05			4.52		
	SABH	4.32			4.32			4.32			3.32			4.14		

					2 5			2 7			4 9					
	SEAI TE	4. 26			4 .2 7			4 .3 0			3 .6 1				4. 22	
	SEAS	4. 36			4 .2 3			4 .3 5			4 .1 9				4. 35	
	SHAS	4. 27			4 .2 4			4 .4 8			3 .7 6				4. 52	
	SGS- CPD	4. 30			4 .6 3			4 .5 0			4 .3 0				4. 50	
Field/ Special ization	Teach er Educat ion	4. 65			4 .5 3			4. 60			4. 24				4. 55	
	Social Scienc e and Huma nities	4. 43			4 .3 2			4. 54			4. 05				4. 44	
	Health and Allied Scienc es	4. 29			4 .2 6			4. 49			3. 78				4. 48	
	Busin ess and Hospit ality Manag ement	4. 35	10. 603	.0 00	4 .2 9	3.8 97	.0 02	4.1 53	.0 01	7.0 17	.0 00	4. 16	3.6 90	.0 03		
	Engin eering and Archit ecture	4. 14			4 .2 3			4. 28			3. 64				4. 29	
	Infor mation Techn ology and Relate	4. 68			4 .4 9			4. 56			3. 69				4. 33	

	d Discipline															
Years in Teaching	< 1 year	4. 71			4 .6 4			4. 69			4. 29			4. 74		
	1 - 3	4. 37			4 .3 6			4. 46			3. 92			4. 40		
	4 - 6	4. 60	4.2 41	.0 03	4 .4 9	1.9 97	.0 96	4. 53	1.2 11	.3 07	4. 14	1.3 41	.2 56	4. 58	3.2 81	.0 12
	7 - 9	4. 69			4 .5 7			4. 63			3. 96			4. 42		
	≥ 10 years	4. 52			4 .3 7			4. 50			3. 96			4. 34		

p < .05 = Significant

Table 3.b
Test of Significant Difference on Teachers' Pedagogical Practices When Grouped by Academic Profile

Academic Profile	Group	Constructivist			Collaborative			Integrative			Reflective			Inquiry-Based		
		Mean	t/F value	p-value	Mean	t/F value	p-value	Mean	t/F value	p-value	Mean	t/F value	p-value	Mean	t/F value	p-value
No. of training attended related to instructional pedagogy	0 - 5	4. 47			4. 39			4. 52			3. 92			4. 43		
	6 - 10	4. 65			4. 54			4. 61			4. 14			4. 57		
	11 - 15	4. 49	2.5 96	.0 37	4. 47	1.7 63	.1 37	4. 51	1. 60 9	.1 73	3. 83	1.8 10	.1 28	4. 47	1. 56 0	.1 86
	16 - 20	4. 33			4. 33			4. 36			4. 17			4. 35		
	≥ 21	4. 45			4. 32			4. 42			4. 16			4. 35		
Type of school from	SUC/LUC	4. 60	3.1 88	.0 43	4. 45	.12 9	.8 79	4. 54	.3 85	.6 81	4. 09	.56 9	.5 67	4. 53	.9 76	.3 78
	Catholic HEIs	4. 45			4. 41			4. 50			3. 97			4. 42		

which bachelor's degree was obtained	Private HEIs	4.59			4.44			4.56			4.04			4.45		
Subject taught	Language and Literature	4.68	5.103	.000	4.62	2.707	.001	4.66	2.609	.001	4.27	3.285	.000	4.60	3.285	.000
	Music, Arts, PE, and Health	4.82			4.65			4.75			4.45			4.68		
	Economics and Livelihood Education	4.83			4.64			4.77			4.25			4.71		
	Mathematics	4.42			4.41			4.46			4.05			4.27		
	Allied Health Sciences	4.34			4.28			4.47			3.85			4.46		
	Christian Formation Education	4.57			4.39			4.54			4.06			4.44		
	Business and Accounting	4.30			4.22			4.24			3.59			4.14		
	Professional Education	4.67			4.17			3.92			3.92			4.25		
	Social Sciences Discipline and General Education	4.65			4.53			4.63			4.39			4.67		

	Research Discipline	3.97			4.20			4.11			3.31			4.17		
	Information Communications Technology	4.70			4.51			4.56			3.76			4.35		
	Law	3.80			3.88			4.21			3.71			4.21		
	Psychology	4.61			4.61			4.56			4.28			4.56		
	Engineering and Applied Sciences	4.20			4.27			4.38			3.74			4.40		
	Hospitality Management	4.45			4.78			4.61			3.66			4.39		
	Architecture	4.21			4.00			4.17			3.00			3.96		
Type of Education	Teacher Education Graduate	4.65			4.55			4.61			4.23			4.55		
	Non-Education Graduate with LET	4.47	20.318	.000	4.53	13.672	.000	4.53	7.735	.001	1.05	15.309	.000	4.20	6.588	.002
	Non-Education Graduate without LET	4.29			4.24			4.38			3.69			4.34		

p<.05=Significant

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents. In terms of personal profile, majority of the respondents are female, twenty-five (25) to twenty-nine (29) years of age, single, bachelor's degree holders, teaching in junior high school, specializing in teacher education, and have been into teaching profession for one (1) to three (3) years. In terms of academic profile, most respondents attended less than five (5) trainings related to instructional pedagogy for the past five (5) years, obtained his/her bachelor's degree in Catholic Higher Education Institutions, taught language and literature, and are teacher education graduates.

Table 2 shows the summary of pedagogical practices of teachers. As shown, constructivist method and integrative method are always practiced by teachers. On the other hand, teachers often practiced collaborative method, reflective method, and inquiry-based method. Among these pedagogical practices, integrative method obtained the highest mean. This implies that integrative method is always practiced over other pedagogical practices because it provides more comprehensive and holistic understanding of a topic by combining different perspectives and approaches. An integrative teacher is characterized to be creative, adaptable, and critical in reasoning (Bati, 2023; Aparicio-Herguedas, Fraile-Aranda, & Rodríguez-Medina, 2023). Without proper integration, learners will not be able to build the competency in skills that are necessary for enduring success. Integrated pedagogies provide learners with a better knowledge of the course material and how to apply what they've learned in the classroom in real-world situations. This, in turn, helps students prepare for their future education, careers, and lives in general. The main characteristics of integrated learning include creativity, flexibility, critical thinking, and teamwork. The learning technique allows a wide range of learning styles, theories, and different intelligences (Anamova & Khvesyuk, 2020; Rizhniak, Pasichnyk, Zavitrenko, Akbash, & Zavitrenko, 2021; Khan & Soomro, 2022).

Table 3.a shows the test of significant difference on teachers' pedagogical practices when grouped by personal profile. It was shown that there is a significant difference on teachers' pedagogical practices when grouped by sex along constructivist method, collaborative method, and integrative method. Also, a significant difference was revealed on teachers' pedagogical practices when grouped by department along constructivist method, collaborative method, integrative method, reflective method, and inquiry-based method. By field/specialization, a significant difference on teacher's pedagogical practices was found along constructivist method, collaborative method, integrative method, reflective method, and inquiry-based method. The findings also revealed that there is a significant difference on teacher's pedagogical practices when grouped by number of years in teaching along constructivist method and inquiry-based method. Lastly, there is no significant difference on teachers' pedagogical practices when grouped by age, civil status, and highest educational attainment. Meanwhile, there is no significant difference on teachers' pedagogical practices when grouped by sex along reflective method and inquiry-based method since the probability is higher than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. The findings highlight the importance of considering the intersecting influences of individual, organizational, and contextual factors in

promoting effective teaching and learning experiences in schools and educational settings. By understanding and addressing the unique needs and preferences of teachers, educational stakeholders can work collaboratively to create supportive environments that foster professional growth, innovation, and student success (Alejandro & David, 2018; Kilag, Tokong, Enriquez, Deiparine, Purisima, & Zamora, 2023).

Table 3.b shows the test of significant difference on teachers' pedagogical practices when grouped by academic profile. It can be gleaned that there is a significant difference on teachers' pedagogical practices when grouped by number of trainings attended related to instructional pedagogy along constructivist method. Findings also revealed that there is a significant difference on teachers' pedagogical practices when grouped by type of school from which bachelor's degree was obtained along constructivist method. It was shown that there is a significant difference on teachers' pedagogical practices when grouped by subject previously taught along constructivist, collaborative, integrative, reflective, and inquiry-based method. By type of education, a significant difference on teachers' pedagogical practices was revealed along constructivist, collaborative, integrative, reflective, and inquiry-based methods. Lastly, it was shown that there is no significant difference on teachers' pedagogical practices when grouped by number of trainings attended related to instructional pedagogy along collaborative, integrative, reflective, and inquiry-based method. By type of school from which bachelor's degree was obtained, no significant difference on teachers' pedagogical practices was found along collaborative, integrative, reflective, and inquiry-based method since the probability value is higher than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. The findings underscore the importance of considering teachers' academic profiles and professional backgrounds when designing teacher training programs and educational interventions aimed at enhancing pedagogical effectiveness. By tailoring professional development initiatives to address the specific needs and experiences of educators, schools and educational institutions can better support teacher growth and improve student learning outcomes (Sancar, Atal, & Deryakulu, 2021); Alkaabi, 2023; Borbajo, Malbas, & Dacanay, 2023). Additionally, understanding how different factors intersect to influence pedagogical practices can inform efforts to create inclusive and effective learning environments that meet the diverse needs of students and teachers alike (Hutchison & McAlister-Shields, 2020; Fuentes, Zelaya, & Madsen, 2021).

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Teachers often practiced the following pedagogies: collaborative, reflective, and inquiry-based methods. However, there is a need to strengthen and master the other pedagogies for holistic teaching to cater the peculiarity of diverse learners amidst the learning constraints.
2. Teachers' pedagogical practices have significant differences along the personal profile such as sex, department, field/ specialization, and number of years in teaching.
3. Teachers' pedagogical practices have significant differences along academic profile such as number of trainings attended related to instructional pedagogy, type of

school from which bachelor's degree was obtained, subject taught, and type of education.

Recommendations

In light with the findings and conclusions presented in the study, the following are recommended:

1. The academic coordinators and program chairs may consider the different pedagogical approaches during their classroom observation among their teachers to ensure that teachers are implementing best practices, to support teacher development, to promote student-centered learning, to improve student engagement, and to foster positive and conducive learning environment.

2. The school academic administrators may consider it in reviewing and revising their classroom observation tool to obtain precise and well-evaluated teaching and learning process. By incorporating these approaches into the observation tool, school academic administrators can ensure that the tool is comprehensive and reflective of current best practices in education. This can lead to more effective teacher evaluations and ultimately improve student learning outcomes.

3. The institution, specifically program implementers, may use it as a benchmark for crafting relevant programs, training/seminars, workshops for teachers which focus on instructional strategies focusing on the five approaches in teaching.

4. The teachers may focus on the frequently utilized instructional strategies and strengthen the mastered approaches to obtain holistic teaching. Thus, mastering the different approaches will significantly help both teachers and learners, likewise the institution to practice culture of excellence in education.

5. The study may look on the experiences of learners regarding the teachers' utilization of instructional pedagogies.

6. The future researchers may conduct another study looking on the significant relationship of pedagogical practices on other variables such as teachers' pedagogical beliefs, teachers' teaching performance, and students' learning performance.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations were employed by the researcher. Informed consent was accomplished by the respondents to ensure the compliance to ethical standards. The

data that were provided by the respondents were treated with utmost confidentiality and anonymity.

Acknowledgments

I highly acknowledge my parents for their unwavering support throughout my journey to complete my degree. Your encouragement, love, and sacrifices have been the driving force behind my academic success, and I am incredibly grateful for everything you have done for me.

REFERENCES

- Alejandro, P., & David, I. (2018). Educational Research and Innovation Teachers as Designers of Learning Environments The Importance of Innovative Pedagogies: The Importance of Innovative Pedagogies. OECD Publishing.
- Ali, R.; Mondal M.; Das, T. (2018). Pedagogy and the role of teachers in the Teaching learning process. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 5 (5).
- Alkaabi, A. M. (2023). Designing Enduring and Impactful Professional Development to Support Teacher Growth. In *Innovations in Teacher Development, Personalized Learning, and Upskilling the Workforce* (pp. 1-23). IGI Global.
- Anamova, R. R., & Khvesyuk, T. M. (2020). The integrated approach to the teaching of geometric-graphical disciplines at the university. *Pedagogika*, 140(4), 172-193.
- Aparicio-Herguedas, J. L., Fraile-Aranda, A., & Rodríguez-Medina, J. (2023). Teaching skills in physical education teacher training: theoretical and factor models. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1), 1-8.
- Archambault, L., Leary, H., & Rice, K. (2022). Pillars of online pedagogy: A framework for teaching in online learning environments. *Educational Psychologist*, 57(3), 178-191.
- Bati, K. (2023). Education of Integrated Science: Discussions on Importance and Teaching Approaches. In *Integrated Education and Learning* (pp. 337-354). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Borbajo, M. N. M., Malbas, M. H., & Dacanay, L. R. (2023). Reforming education: the global impact of integrating artificial intelligence in the classroom environment. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education* (2993-2769), 1(5), 16-27.
- Brown, B. A., Boda, P., Lemmi, C., & Monroe, X. (2019). Moving culturally relevant pedagogy from theory to practice: Exploring teachers' application of culturally relevant education in science and mathematics. *Urban Education*, 54(6), 775-803.
- Butola, L. K. (2021). E-learning-a new trend of learning in 21st century during COVID-19 pandemic. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology*, 15(1), 423
- Compayré, G., & Payne, W. H. (2015). *The history of pedagogy*. Routledge.
- Courtney, S. A., Miller, M. E., & Gisondo, M. J. (2022). The Impact of COVID-19 on Teachers' Integration of Digital Technology. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 14(4), ep387

- De los Reyes, E. J., Blannin, J., Cohrssen, C., & Mahat, M. (2022). Resilience of higher education academics in the time of 21st century pandemics: a narrative review. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 44(1), 39-56.
- Ezra, O., Cohen, A., Bronshtein, A., Gabbay, H., & Baruth, O. (2021). Equity factors during the COVID-19 pandemic: Difficulties in emergency remote teaching (ert) through online learning. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(6), 7657-7681.
- Fuentes, M. A., Zelaya, D. G., & Madsen, J. W. (2021). Rethinking the course syllabus: Considerations for promoting equity, diversity, and inclusion. *Teaching of Psychology*, 48(1), 69-79.
- Ginsburg, M. B., & Megahed, N. M. (2021). Global discourses and educational reform in Egypt: The case of active-learning pedagogies. In *Educational Scholarship across the Mediterranean* (pp. 171-195). Brill.
- Hutchison, L., & McAlister-Shields, L. (2020). Culturally responsive teaching: Its application in higher education environments. *Education Sciences*, 10(5), 124.
- Khan, M., & Soomro, N. H. (2022). INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING ENGLISH: TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVES AND PRACTICES. *Pakistan Journal of Educational Research*, 5(2).
- Kilag, O. K., Tokong, C., Enriquez, B., Deiparine, J., Purisima, R., & Zamora, M. (2023). School Leaders: The Extent of Management Empowerment and Its Impact on Teacher and School Effectiveness. *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education (2994-9521)*, 1(1), 127-140.
- LaTour, K. A., & Noel, H. N. (2021). Self-directed learning online: An opportunity to binge. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 43(2), 174-188.
- O'Keefe, L., Rafferty, J., Gunder, A., & Vignare, K. (2020). *Delivering High-Quality Instruction Online in Response to COVID-19: Faculty Playbook*. Online Learning Consortium
- Pham, J. H., & Philip, T. M. (2021). Shifting education reform towards anti-racist and intersectional visions of justice: A study of pedagogies of organizing by a teacher of color. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 30(1), 27-51
- Putri, S., & Elihami, E. (2021). The concept andragogy and pedagogy: e-learning model during covid-19 pandemic. *Jurnal Edukasi Nonformal*, 2(1), 18-24.
- Reimers, F. M. (2022). Learning from a pandemic. The impact of COVID-19 on education around the world. In *Primary and secondary education during COVID-19* (pp. 1-37). Springer, Cham.
- Rippé, C. B., Weisfeld-Spolter, S., Yurova, Y., & Kemp, A. (2021). Pandemic pedagogy for the new normal: Fostering perceived control during COVID-19. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 43(2), 260-276.
- Rizhniak, R., Pasichnyk, N., Zavitrenko, D., Akbash, K., & Zavitrenko, A. R. T. E. M. (2021). The Implementation of an Integrative Approach to Learning with the Use of Integrated Images. *Revista Romaneasca pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 13(1), 281-297.
- Sancar, R., Atal, D., & Deryakulu, D. (2021). A new framework for teachers' professional development. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 101, 103305.
- Sato, M., & Loewen, S. (2019). Do teachers care about research? The research-pedagogy dialogue. *ELT Journal*, 73(1), 1-10.
- Terenko, O., & Ogienko, O. (2020). How to Teach Pedagogy Courses Online at University in COVID-19 Pandemic: Search for Answers. *Romanian Journal for Multidimensional Education/Revista Romaneasca pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 12.

- UNESCO (2021). When schools shut: Gendered impacts of COVID-19 school closures. Paris.
- United Nations (2020). Policy Brief: Education during COVID-19 and beyond.
- Usanov, F., & Qayumov, B. (2020). The eight ways to advance pedagogy to the next level. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2020(1), 181-190.
- Yates, A., Starkey, L., Egerton, B., & Flueggen, F. (2021). High school students' experience of online learning during Covid-19: the influence of technology and pedagogy. *Technology, Pedagogy and Education*, 30(1), 59-73.